

9 - 13 September 2024
Stellenbosch | South Africa

15th Aquaculture Association of Southern Africa Conference (AASA)

co-hosted by
EU Horizon 2020
ASTRAL
(All Atlantic Ocean
Sustainable, Profitable &
Resilient Aquaculture)

We would like to thank our sponsors:

Aquaculture Association of Southern Africa

WOMEN IN AQUACULTURE. FROM PLANS TO ACTIONS: THE JOURNEY OF THE ASTRAL PROJECT

Ospina-Alvarez, N, LiChen, T, Waniko, S & Ravagnan E

AIR Centre - Atlantic International Research Centre. Terceira Island, Azores, Portugal
natalia.ospina@aircentre.org

Seventy per cent of the global aquaculture workforce is comprised of women; however, the vast majority of production management roles are occupied by men. One contributing factor to the invisibility of women in aquaculture policy is the insufficient data on their participation and the lack of gender-specific training.

Under the approach of sustainable aquaculture, ASTRAL has taken steps to address the disparity pointed out above by empowering women in the aquaculture industry through targeted awareness campaigns and specialized training programs aimed at enhancing the visibility and role of women in this sector.

ASTRAL delivered a gender-sensitive Human Capital Development Plan (HUCAP) to improve professional skills and create a highly trained workforce. From 2021 to 2024, 13 apprenticeships, 10 training courses, and 2 summer/winter schools have been carried out. A total of 306 training certificates have been issued to trainees from 13 different countries within the framework of the ASTRAL HUCAP, 60% of which were awarded to women. Additionally, a workshop focused specifically on Sensitization and Women Mainstreaming into Aquaculture was organised in Nigeria in 2022, training 323 women in specific aspects of aquaculture production and management.

Promoting women as equal and productive partners has significant impacts on improving household nutrition and living standards, and thus is crucial to reaching the UN SDG2 (end hunger, achieve food security and improved nutrition, and promote sustainable agriculture) and SDG5 (achieve gender equality and empower all girls and women). This is the contribution of ASTRAL to support the involvement and empower women in aquaculture, promoting and supporting their entry into new and emerging markets, as well as profitable enterprises and businesses in Atlantic countries.

ASTRAL -*All Atlantic Ocean Sustainable, Profitable and Resilient Aquaculture*- is an EU H2020 project (GA 863034) funded under the Blue Growth programme.

Further information: www.astral-project.eu/